

Analysis of the Effect of Knowledge, Attitudes, and Support on the Preparedness of the Team for Exceptional Events and Outbreaks at Public Health Center the Bengkulu Province

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ABSTRACT

Background: Community Extraordinary events need to be anticipated by preparing a team to respond quickly to exceptional circumstances and outbreaks at each health center, and it is necessary to increase the capacity of the special personnel of the Rapid Action Team (RAT). What is the preparedness of the fast-moving team to respond to the prevention and control of outbreaks at the Public Health center.

Materials/Methods: Quantitative research with a cross-sectional approach was implemented to determine the effect of knowledge, attitude, and support on the preparedness of the Team for Extraordinary Events in Health Centers in Bengkulu Province. The population of the Rapid Action Team training participants was 10 batches. A sample of 153 respondents, analysis of linear and multiple regression data using SPSS 22 to analyze the effect of knowledge, attitudes, and support on the preparedness of the TGC Team.

Result: The team must prepare themselves by compiling and training in applying standard operating procedures (SOP) for handling extraordinary events for each disease that can potentially be an exceptional circumstance (KLB). The fast-moving team must prepare themselves by conducting simulations to find out their readiness by evaluating each simulation result to improve the team's preparedness. The fast action team (RAT) for handling outbreaks and outbreaks at the Puskesmas is a policy that must be established by the decision of the authorized official.

Conclusion: The Rapid action team (RAT) for handling extraordinary events and outbreaks at the Public health center is a policy that must be established by the decision of the authorized official so that it is more motivated and facilitates the need for Team preparedness for Extraordinary Events (KLB). The team is expected to carry out routine simulations for team preparedness in handling extraordinary events.

KEYWORDS: Knowledge, Attitude, Support, Rapid Action Team Preparedness

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INTRODUCTION

Exceptional Events of infectious diseases and food poisoning are still a public health problem. They can cause a large number of morbidity and mortality, absorb an enormous budget in response efforts, impact the economic sector and tourism and have the potential to spread across districts/cities, provinces, and even between countries. Extraordinary events must be detected early and followed by fast and appropriate action. There need to be identified threats and vulnerable conditions that increase the risk of an outbreak. It is necessary to increase vigilance and preparedness for possible outbreaks.

In minimizing losses due to disasters that occur, the role of health workers who are responsive and ready is needed(1).

The exceptional events must be anticipated by preparing a team at each Health Center. It is urgently needed to increase the capacity of the Health Center staff, specifically for the Rapid Action Team (RAT), for handling extraordinary events to carry out a response to prevent and deal with exceptional circumstances in the work area of the Health Center. Knowledge, attitudes, and preparedness influence the preparedness factor for health workers in handling emergency flood disasters (2). Training for rapid acting Team (RAT)

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staff at the Health Center to improve competence in assisting in managing outbreaks and outbreaks in their respective work areas. After participating in the training, it is hoped that fast-moving teams can form and prepare team by conducting socialization, preparing standard operating procedures (SOP), and preparing simulations to find out the Team's preparedness to prevent and deal with diseases that have the potential to occur in outbreaks in the Puskesmas area.

Management of extraordinary events and outbreaks of infectious diseases is regulated in Law Number 4 of 1984 concerning Outbreaks of Infectious Diseases, Government Regulation No.40 of 1991 concerning Control of Outbreaks of Infectious Diseases, Minister of Health Regulation No. 501 of 2010 concerning Certain Diseases that Can Cause Plague Exceptional events must be detected early, followed by quick and appropriate action. It is necessary to identify the threat of an outbreak and vulnerable conditions that increase the risk, so that awareness and preparedness can be increased for the possibility of an outbreak. On this basis, it is necessary to increase the capacity of the Puskesmas staff, specifically for the Extraordinary Events Rapid Action Team (RAT), to respond to the prevention and management of outbreaks in the working area of Puskesmas. Increasing staff capacity can be increased through training for RAT staff at the Community Health Centers to improve competence in handling outbreaks and/or epidemics in their respective work areas.

Health Center staff trained in the Rapid Response Team for Extraordinary Events and Epidemic Management are required to form and prepare a Team so they can carry out their duties and functions. How is the team's preparedness to act quickly to deal with extraordinary events and outbreaks at the Puskesmas? It is necessary to analyze the influence of

knowledge, attitudes, and support on the Team's preparedness.

METHODS

Quantitative research method with a cross-sectional approach to determine the effect of knowledge, attitude, and support on the Team for Extraordinary Events preparedness at the Bengkulu Province Health Center. Knowledge, attitude, and support as independent variables, and the readiness of the Team for Extraordinary Events Rapid Action Team as the dependent variable. Data collection used an instrument that contained a list of knowledge questions and attitudes of the team to quickly respond to outbreaks, support from leaders, colleagues, cross-sectors, and team preparedness. The population of this study was 10 batches (300 participants) of training participants for extraordinary events and outbreaks. The study sample consisted of 153 respondents.

Analysis of linear and multiple regression data using SPSS 22, to analyze the effect of knowledge, attitudes, and support on the preparedness of the RAT. The Multiple Linear Regression Test analysis aims to determine whether or not there is an influence of two or more independent variables.

RESULTS

The results of the univariate analysis of the independent and dependent variables were that the independent variables had excellent average knowledge (83.6%), good average attitudes (96.7%), good average support (90.8%), and fewer preparedness criteria sufficient (64.7%).

The results of the Chi-square test analysis aim to determine the effect of the independent variables' Knowledge, Attitude, and Support on the dependent variable, the preparedness of the Cepa Mobility Team can be seen in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1. Chi-Square Test

		Value	df	Asymp. Sig.(2-sided)
Knowledge	Pearson Chi-Square	5,392 ^a	2	,067
Attitude	Pearson Chi-Square	4,368 ^a	4	,359
Support	Pearson Chi-Square	8,368 ^a	4	,079

Source: Processed data

The results of table 1. obtained a p-value > 0.05. It can be concluded that there was no influence of knowledge, attitudes, and support on the team's preparedness to act quickly for outbreaks and outbreaks. Knowing that there is a

similarity in the impact of knowledge, attitude, and support on the readiness of the Fast Action Team, a Multivariate Test analysis was carried out.

Table 2. Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Value	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Readiness	Pillai's Trace	,092	2,393	,028	,046
	Wilks' Lambda	,909	2,406	,028	,047
	Hotelling's Trace	,099	2,418	,027	,047
	Roy's Largest Root	,084	4,185	,007	,078

Source: Processed data

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Based on Table 2. The output results show that the p-value for Wilks Lambda is 2.406. It can be concluded that the p-value > 0.05, meaning that the independent variables of knowledge, attitudes, and support have the same effect on the preparedness of the Fast Action Team.

DISCUSSION

The results of the analysis of knowledge, attitudes, and support did not affect the preparedness of the rapid response team in managing outbreaks and outbreaks at the Community Health Center. These results are different from Adisah (2022), who says there is a relationship between the Rapid action team (RAT) with the preparedness of health workers in management based on knowledge, attitude, and practice/experience (2). The results of the univariate analysis of good average knowledge (83.6%), good average attitude (96.7%), good average support (90.8%), and insufficient and sufficient preparedness (64.7%). Knowledge of the fast-action Team is suitable for preparing to carry out Team functions. The attitude of the Team members is excellent in supporting the implementation of team functions. The results of Yunus' research (2021) say that the preparedness factor for health workers is influenced by knowledge, attitude, and preparedness in handling emergencies (2).

The team must prepare themselves by compiling and training in applying standard operating procedures (SOP) for handling extraordinary events for each disease that has the potential for an exceptional event. Application of each standard, ability to identify priority resource elements relevant to routine essential health and public health activities, assist and support implementing ability standards to improve day to day effectiveness to build a stronger foundation against outbreaks. Public health agencies can demonstrate capabilities through training, encouraging teams to strategically incorporate routine activities into pilot projects to test and evaluate emergency preparedness and rapid response capacities (4). The fast-moving team must prepare themselves by conducting simulations of extraordinary events integrated with daily tasks at the Puskesmas, so that they can determine readiness by evaluating each simulation result and improving it for the Team's preparedness.

Team framework in two ways, first, the type of team that contributes to the quality and safety of patient care; second, build each other to develop an ideal team state. Frameworks and strategies can guide where and how to target development efforts (5). The presented solutions help teams manage challenges at multiple levels and emphasize the importance of targeting the root causes of team problems. Focus on setting up and executing team processes, setting aside specific time for team development, and training team skills such as technical skills (5).

The Rapid action team (RAT) for handling outbreaks and outbreaks at the Puskesmas is a policy that must be stipulated by the decision of an authorized official, in this case, at least at the head of the district/city Health Office. The success of policy implementation often depends on a supporter who can help secure the necessary resources and motivate staff to create activity opportunities. Local health officials have become strong advocates for policies and programs encouraging greater physical activity. Policy mechanisms facilitate the implementation of projects that increase activity (6). Institutionalizing and embedding the culture and policies of the organization, as well as the entire system, will ensure increased adaptability, capacity, and innovation for greater responsiveness, resilience, and equity of health services after this pandemic is over (7). The team for the rapid response to extraordinary events (LKB) and outbreaks needs to be established with a policy so that the team can be more motivated to be prepared in dealing with potential incidents beyond the cost of disease at the Puskesmas.

The global threat of COVID-19 continues to emerge. It is essential to increase the awareness and preparedness of community members who are targeted, especially those who are less educated. Educational interventions are urgently needed to reach targeted populations beyond borders, and further action is required. The results of this study highlight the growing need for the adoption of innovative local strategies to increase general public awareness related to COVID-19 and prevention practices to meet elimination goals (8). Knowledge and preparedness are translated into better methods for preventing COVID-19, including full control over COVID-19, investing in various COVID-19 prevention efforts, health education, and innovative strategies based on local evidence to increase public awareness and improve prevention practices (8). Preparedness The Rapid Action Team must get used to conducting simulations and provide increased knowledge and understanding regarding efforts to prevent and control outbreaks and outbreaks. Interventions undertaken or supported by the government are more successful, such as multi-factorial interventions. In generalizing interventions that have proven effective under certain conditions, a number of target population factors must be taken into account, including socioeconomic and political circumstances, the level of government support that can be expected, culture and religion, and health systems (9).

Pandemic preparedness refers to a government's ability to anticipate pandemics before they occur and prepare for public health emergencies by developing the proper knowledge and capacities. Understanding hazards and threats and building capacity for review and risk assessment makes it possible to target prevention policies and mitigation programs better to reduce vulnerability to risk (10). A risk management protocol should be established to

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establish standard operating procedures and predetermined plans for dealing with a pandemic. The main phases of the risk cycle in which evaluation can be carried out The lesson learned is crisis management, namely the policies and actions governments put in place to deal with when a crisis occurs. Crisis management requires the correct response at the right time and in a coordinated way across the government (10). Establishing a rapid action team as a policy to anticipate, prevent and deal with extraordinary events is very much following the right and fast response from the government to protect the public.

While emergency risk management and preparedness helps make health systems more resilient, it is essential to recognize investments in underlying health system capacity, as emergency preparedness requires health workers with the appropriate skills and competencies that are equitably distributed. This workforce should be well-paid, supported, and motivated to perform routine and emergency tasks (11). The policy of forming a fast-acting team will receive support to improve skills and boost the team always to be prepared to prevent and deal with extraordinary events and outbreaks.

Social contextual factors influence the success and failure of technology dissemination for public health workers in the health care system. The goal is to broadly describe the social system's influence in a context that contributes to the success or failure of public health interventions (12). It is essential to improve people's attitudes towards disaster preparedness; response efficacy should help raise awareness about disaster preparedness and mitigation. A response's effectiveness is built on a community's ability to take action to reduce risk and increase awareness of disaster preparedness. Determinants that can help raise awareness of the efficacy of responses related to disaster preparedness by facilitating risk communication (13). In an effort to prevent and deal with extraordinary events, the fast-moving team must communicate with the community to reduce risks in the event of an extraordinary event and outbreak.

CONCLUSION

The Rapid action team (RAT) for handling extraordinary events and outbreaks at the Puskesmas is a policy that must be established by the decision of the authorized official so that it is more motivated and facilitates the need for Team preparedness for Extraordinary Events. The team must prepare a standard operating procedure (SOP) for each potential disease and conduct simulations regularly by involving all internal and external elements of the Puskesmas that play a role in managing extraordinary events.

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